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DIAGNOSIS OF ACTIVE MAGNETIC BEARING SYSTEM FAULTS USING PRINCIPAL COMPONENT ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Active Magnetic Bearings (AMBs) endure rotating member without any frictional loss. Therefore compared to the journal and hydrodynamic bearings, AMBs have benefits of reduced frictional losses as a result they can support high speed rotor. Stable working operation of AMB is principally depends on the working condition of its position sensors, actuators and controller. Therefore sensors and actuators are the important working elements of AMB system. Fault or failure in any one the sensor or actuator of AMB system can results in undesired rotor dynamics behaviour. Hence to ensure the safe operation and authentic performance of AMB system, fault detection and diagnosis (FDD) of sensors and actuators is very much essential. Principal component analysis (PCA) is a model free and robust statistical technique which can detect and diagnose the faults in engineering systems with high accuracy. Therefore, in the present work, PCA based FDD methodology is employed to detection and diagnosis of AMB sensors and actuators fault. Simulations have been carried out to diagnose the sensor and actuator faults of AMB system. Q-statistic or square prediction error is used for bias and noise faults.

Keywords: Active Magnetic Bearing (AMB), Fault detection and diagnosis (FDD), Principal component analysis (PCA), Sensors and actuators faults.

I. INTRODUCTION

Active magnetic bearing (AMB) is a mechatronic device which levitates the rotor by manipulating the attractive electromagnetic forces. Due to its ability in operating without mechanical friction losses between the rotor and stator and high-precision operation, they are most suitable for high speed application such as turbo machinery and machine tools [15]. The desired operation of AMB mainly depends on performance of displacement sensors and actuators of the system. Fault or failure of any one of the sensor and actuator can result in destructive rotor dynamics behaviour. Therefore, in order to avoid such failure of entire system, fault detection and diagnosis (FDD) of AMBs under its operating condition becomes very essential.

In the present, work an attempt is made to detect and diagnose the sensor and actuator faults

in AMBs. Many FDD methods for AMBs have been discussed in the literature. Kim and Lee [11] proposed state estimation FDD method to detect sensor faults in AMBs. An abrupt change in transient state and dual faults can't be detected by this methodology. Losch [12] used position estimation technique to detect the sensor faults in AMBs. Both sensor and actuator faults can be diagnosed by this methodology, while it also requires redundant sensors to diagnose multiple sensors faults. Hu et al. [8] used multi value logic algebra method to identifying the sensor faults in AMBs, but it was incapable to diagnosed dual fault at a time. Cade et al. [4] implemented wavelet analysis technique (digital signal processing approach) to identify the rotor displacement in AMBs. Garcia et al. [6] used redundancy based FDD method to formulate and predict sensor malfunction and abnormal operating conditions in AMBs, however multiple. Sensor faults can't be

predicted by this methodology. Tsai et al. [16] applied Luenberger state estimation technique to diagnose the multiple sensor faults, by using the mathematical model of AMBs. Beckerle et al. [3] proposed balancing filter approach based on parity equation to identify unknown faulty states in AMBs. This method distinguished faulty states clearly which are difficult by model based methods but increased complexity of system due to designing of filters.

However, all the above discussed FDD methods are model and redundancy based, they required the precise mathematical modelling as well as result in increased complexity and cost of AMB system. Therefore, in this paper, model-free Principal Components Analysis (PCA) based FDD method has been proposed for AMB sensors and actuators faults diagnosis. PCA is a simple multivariable statistical method with very high dimensional accuracy [5]. Both stationary and dynamic faults in the system can be detected and isolated by correlating data into lower dimensional subspace [17]. Due to the complexity of the system, it may not always be possible to represent a system in terms of accurate mathematical model while PCA does not require the mathematical model of the system.

II. FAULTS IN AMBs

Fault is defined as the unpermitted deviations of a signal from its normal working state [9]. Therefore fault is the state that may lead to unsatisfactory operation or failure of the entire system.

Faults in AMB system can be broadly classified as external and internal faults. This classification then relates to the way in which the fault can be dealt with its occurrence. A fault may be termed external if its dynamic effect can be considered as an external disturbance applied to the system. When such a fault occurs, the resulting response of the system will introduce abnormal components in measured signals. Internal faults cannot be represented by external disturbances as they affect the actuation, measurement or control processes and thereby the system dynamics.

Sensors and actuators are the important components of AMB system. Their performance directly affects the entire operation of the system. Sensor faults occur due to various factors, such as manufacturing defects, wear and tear with long term usage and incorrect calibration or mishandling. Basically, there are three types of faults in sensors and actuators [11]:

- (a) Bias fault
- (b) Multiplicative fault
- (c) Noise fault

Bias fault: A constant offset is observed from nominal state of sensor signal statistics. Mathematically it is governed by Eq.(1).

$$Y_f = X + \beta + \text{noise} \tag{1}$$

Multiplicative fault: Magnitude is increased by a factor from the nominal state of sensor signal statistics. It is governed by Eq.(2).

$$Y_f = \alpha(t) X \tag{2}$$

Noise fault: A random time series is observed. It may be represented as Eq.(3)

$$Y_f = \text{noise} \tag{3}$$

III. MODELLING OF EIGHT-POLE MAGNETIC BEARING

Eight-pole heteropolar configuration of the AMB is considered in the present work. Geometry of eight-pole magnetic bearing is shown in Fig.1. All the poles of the AMB are considered identical. Forces generated along the positive X and Y axes [1] are given by Eqs.4 and(5):

$$F_x = \sum_{j=1}^8 \frac{\phi_j^2}{2\mu_0 A_j} \cos \theta_j \tag{4}$$

$$F_y = \sum_{j=1}^8 \frac{\phi_j^2}{2\mu_0 A_j} \sin \theta_j \tag{5}$$

where, μ_0 is the magnetic permeability of free space, ϕ_j , A_j and θ_j are the magnetic flux, pole face area and pole orientation angle of the j th pole respectively.

Fig.1 Eight-pole magnetic bearing geometry.

In the present work Fuzzy logic controller (FLC) is used to obtain the stable rotor position of AMBs. Bias current together with control current is supplied separately to each pole of eight-pole AMBs. Block diagram of fuzzy logic controller for AMBs is shown in Fig.2. where, $r(t)$ and $y(t)$ are the reference and current position of rotor centre respectively. $e(t)$ and de/dt are error and rate change of error in rotor centre position respectively. I_c , I_b and I are the control current, bias current and total current supplied to each coil of AMB system respectively.

Fig.2 Fuzzy logic controller

IV. PRINCIPAL COMPONENT ANALYSIS (PCA)

PCA is a multivariate statistical analysis method [5]. A principal component is defined as a linear transformation of the original variables into new set of variables. Original variables are normally correlated while new variables are uncorrelated or orthogonal to each other. Variables in modern engineering system are multi-dimensional and correlated. Due to the redundancy of the variables, the original variables can be represented by smaller number of principal components. PCA uses latent variables instead of every measured variable in the process so they can better explain the behaviour of the process. Instead of analyzing all the variables, the PCA method focuses on analyzing these principal components when monitoring the condition of a system.

In PCA based FDD technique, Q-statistic or square prediction error is evaluated for the new data, using the principal components obtained from the training data. Now this Q-statistic value is used as an index for the fault diagnosis. Upper limit of threshold value for Q-statistic is statistically determined from the training data by using Jackson and Mudholkar method in the residual subspace [5]. When no fault exists, the Q-statistic is less than upper limit of threshold, which represents the normal state of the system. On the other hand, when fault exist, the correlation among the measurements of the variables will be destroyed, and a higher value of Q-statistic which exceeds the threshold limit is generated. This indicates a faulty

state of the system. Once the fault is detected using Q-statistic then Q-Statistic plot of the faulty element is plotted with respect to time to diagnosis the type of fault i.e. bias, multiplicative or noise fault.

PCA model development

Step I: Normalization of the data. First data is centered into zero mean and then into unit variance [14]. Centering is done by subtracting the mean of each column of the matrix X from corresponding element of that column given by Eq.(6).

$$X_{\text{cent}} = [\{x_{1j} - \text{mean}(x_{1j})\} \{x_{2j} - \text{mean}(x_{2j})\} \dots \{x_{nj} - \text{mean}(x_{nj})\}]_{n \times m} \quad (6)$$

Then each column of the mean centered matrix is divided by the corresponding column's standard deviation given by Eq.(7)

$$X_{\text{std}} = [\{x_{1j} / \text{std}(x_{1j})\} \{x_{2j} / \text{std}(x_{2j})\} \dots \{x_{nj} / \text{std}(x_{nj})\}]_{n \times m} \quad (7)$$

Step II: Calculate the covariance matrix C . The covariance matrix is given by Eq.(8).

$$C = \frac{X_{\text{std}}' \times X_{\text{std}}}{n - 1} \quad (8)$$

where, covariance matrix C is real symmetrical matrix.

Step III: Finding the loading vectors (P) using Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) of covariance matrix C given by Eq.(9).

$$[P, S, P'] = SVD(C) = P \times S \times P' \quad (9)$$

With P satisfying condition $PP' = P'P = I$ (Identity matrix)

where the diagonal matrix S contains the non-negative real eigenvalues arranged in the descending order of their magnitude. In order to minimize the effect of fault loading vectors only the largest Eigen values are considered.

The Principal Components (PCs) can be construct as linear transformation of X by combining P in the following manner given by Eqs.(10).

$$T = XP \quad (10)$$

Step IV: Finding out optimal numbers of principal components.

Optimal numbers of principal components are selected based on the **Scree Plot** method as shown in Fig.4. It is a graphical method in which a plot of

the eigenvalues in descending order v/s principal components is used to determine PCs and looks for a 'big gap' or an 'elbow' in the graph to determine the cut-off.

If a principal components retain in PCA model are chosen, then retaining loading matrix is given by Eq.(10):

$$\hat{P} = P(1:m, 1:a) \quad (11)$$

Step V: Decomposition of measurement space into principal components subspace and residual subspace. Once the number of principal components (k) is determined, the data matrix D can be expressed as Eq.(12):

$$D = TP^T = [T\tilde{T}] [\hat{P}P]^T \quad (12)$$

where, $\hat{T} \in R^{n \times k}$ and $\tilde{T} \in R^{n \times (m-k)}$, are matrices containing the (k) retained principal components and the ($m-k$) ignored principal components, respectively, and the matrices $\hat{P} \in R^{m \times k}$ and $\tilde{P} \in R^{m \times (m-k)}$ are matrices containing the (k) retained eigenvectors and the ($m-k$) ignored eigenvectors, respectively. Expanding equation above Eq. (12), we get Eq.(13):

$$D = \hat{T}\hat{P}^T + \tilde{T}\tilde{P}^T = D\hat{P}\hat{P}^T + D(I_m - \hat{P}\hat{P}^T) = \hat{D} + E \quad (13)$$

As shown in Eq. (13), a measured vector D can be expressed using PCA as the sum of two orthogonal parts, approximated vector \hat{D} and residual vector E .

Step V: To calculate the threshold of Q statistic or square prediction error (SPE) in residual subspace [7].

Upper limit of Q statistic is calculated using Jackson & Mudholkar formula according Eq.(14):

$$Q_\alpha = se_1 \left[\frac{h_0 C_\alpha \sqrt{2se_2}}{se_1} + 1 + \frac{se_2 h_0 (1-h_0)}{se_1^2} \right]^{\frac{1}{h_0}} \text{ with } se_i = \sum_{j=a+1}^m \lambda_j^i \quad (14)$$

Where, $i=1, 2 \ \& \ 3$ $h_0 = 1 - \frac{2se_1 se_3}{3se_2^2}$

where, $C_\alpha = 100(1 - \alpha)$ the value of the normal distribution with α level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

Data generation

Simulation model of AMB with Fuzzy logic controller developed in MATLAB programming environment is used for generating the training data. Various displaced positions of the rotor are considered and the corresponding currents from the actuator to all the coils of AMB are noted. The

trajectories of rotor from the displaced position to the stable position in all four quadrants of XY-plane are shown in Fig.3. There are totally 32 displaced rotor positions are considered. For each displaced rotor position, data of 10 variables (8 actuators and 2 position sensors) are noted in 100 equal time intervals starting from displaced position to stable position of the rotor.

The training data is arranged in the form of a matrix given by Eq.(15). (10)

$$X = [I_1 \ I_2 \ I_3 \ I_4 \ I_5 \ I_6 \ I_7 \ I_8 \ X \ Y]_{3200 \times 10} \quad (15)$$

where, $I_1, I_2, I_3, I_4, I_5, I_6, I_7, I_8$ are currents to all the eight-pole from actuators and X, Y are displace position of the rotor along X and Y axis read from the position sensors respectively. (0.11)

Fig.3 Rotor trajectory in XY-plane

Training of PCA model

Three thousand two hundred samples under normal operating condition were used to construct training matrix (X). Each sample consists of ten variables ($I_1, I_2, I_3, I_4, I_5, I_6, I_7, I_8, X, Y$) eight actuators and two displacement sensors. Now this training data is used to find out the optimal number of principal components using PCA model. Because variables are in different units, therefore each column is normalized to zero mean and unit variance. To determine the optimal number of principal components of PCA model SCREE test [5] as shown in Fig.4 is used. A knee evidently exists between third and fourth PCs, therefore four PCs are retained. The upper limit (threshold) of Q-statistic is determined as 12.6636 by taking the confidence level 95%.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Various simulation tests were conducted to verify the PCA strategy for detecting and diagnosing actuators and displacement sensors faults of AMB system.

Fig.4 Scree plot

Detection and diagnosis of bias fault

In **Test-1**, bias (7%) fault was added at time 0.005 s in first actuator of AMB system. Due to this fault the Q-statistic value is increased significantly and exceeded the threshold limit. It found that fault is detected in first actuator soon after the fault occurred as shown in the Fig.5, based on Q-Statistic value of new test data is more than the threshold limit of Q-statistic value of normal operating data. To diagnose the type of the fault (i.e. bias or multiplicative) in the faulty actuator, Q-statistic value is plotted with respect to time as shown in Fig.6.

It can be observed that once the fault has occurred, Q-statistic value is increased and exceeded the threshold limit and then it becomes constant with respect to time. It indicates that there is a bias fault in the first actuator. Further numerical difference between faulty and normal data is calculated. Now standard deviation is finding out of this deviation to diagnose the type of fault of particular actuator or sensor. If standard deviation comes out zero or approximately zero, indicates bias fault.

Fig.5 Q-statistic plot of simulation Test-1 for fault detection

Fig.6 Q-statistic plot of simulation Test-1 for fault diagnosis

Detection and diagnosis of noise fault

In **Test-2**, another noise addition was introduced at time 0.005 s in displacement sensor along Y-axis of AMB system. Fig.7 shows detection of fault in position sensor along Y-axis. From Fig.8, it can be observed that the Q-statistic value of the faulty sensor fluctuates randomly with respect to time. It indicates that there is noise fault.

Fig.7 Q-statistic plot of simulation Test-2 for fault detection

Fig.8 Q-statistic plot of simulation Test-2 for fault diagnosis

VI. CONCLUSION

In the present work, principal component analysis based fault detection and diagnosis methodology has been proposed to detect and diagnose actuator and sensor faults of AMB system. Q-statistic or square prediction error evaluated from the principal components is utilized to detect the actuator and sensor fault of AMB. Once the fault is detected, Q-statistic plot with respect to time have been employed to diagnose the type of fault (i.e. bias, multiplicative or noise). The simulation results show that the proposed PCA based fault detection and diagnosis technique can effectively detect and diagnose different types of faults in AMB system components.

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